

SOCIAL RISKS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR MERLIN PET BOTTLE/TRAY PRODUCTION

Stakeholder category	Subcategory	Waste collection and sorting (Spain)	MLT recycling/depolymerisation (Netherlands)	PET polymerisation (Netherlands)	PET bottle and tray production (Spain)
Worker	Health and safety	Low risk	Medium risk	Low risk	Low risk
Local community	Health and safety living conditions	Very low risk	Very low risk	Very low risk	Very low risk
	Local employment	High risk	Low risk	Low risk	High risk
	Community engagement	Very low risk	Low risk	Very low risk	Low risk
Value chain actors	Supplier relationship	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	No data
	Wealth distribution	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk
	Promoting social responsibility	Very low risk	Low risk	Very low risk	Low risk
Consumer	Feedback mechanism	Very low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk
	Transparency	Very low risk	Very low risk	Very low risk	Medium
	Health and safety	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk
	End-of-life responsibility	Very low risk	Very low risk	Very low risk	Very low risk
Society	Technology development	Very low risk	Very low risk	Very low risk	Very low risk
	Contribution to economic development	Low opportunity	Medium opportunity	Medium opportunity	Medium opportunity
Governmental bodies	Support to circular economy	High opportunity	High opportunity	High opportunity	High opportunity